

Arctic everyday lives (Reetta Toivanen)

This dataset consists of handwritten notes and some recordings of interviews and saved facebook discussions with persons living in the Finnish Arctic. The notes consists of observations and discussions with several persons, recorded interviews of partially transcribed discussions and the facebook-discussions are from different Facebook-groups where people discuss their identity and belonging.

- Dates: 2018-2023
- Keywords: Sámi, Indigenous, Arctic, Solidarity, Belonging, Green transition)
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 - Toivanen, R. (2020). Rannikon assimiloituneet saamelaiset: Riddu Riddu Festivála kielen ja kulttuurin elvytyksessä. *Kulttuurintutkimus*, 37(1-2), 116-124. <https://journal.fi/kulttuurintutkimus/article/view/98101/57983>.
 - Toivanen, R., & Fabritius, N. (2020). Arctic youth transcending notions of ‘culture’ and ‘nature’: emancipative discourses of place for cultural sustainability. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 43, 58-64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2020.02.003>.
 - Toivanen, R., & Stammler, F. (Eds.) (2021). *Young People, Wellbeing and Placemaking in the Arctic*. (1 ed.) (Routledge Research in Polar Regions). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003110019>.
 - Toivanen, R., & Cambou, D. (2021). Human Rights. In C. P. Krieg, & R. Toivanen (Eds.), *Situating Sustainability: A Handbook of Concepts and Contexts* (pp. 51-62). Helsinki University Press. <https://doi.org/10.33134/HUP-14-4>.
 - Toivanen, R. (2022). Protecting indigenous identities? An example of cultural expertise on sámi identity. *Legal pluralism and critical social analysis*, 54(2-3), 210-230. <https://doi.org/10.1080/27706869.2022.2151167>
 - Toivanen, R. (2025). Indigenous Climate Inequalities: A Case Study with the Arctic Sámi Peoples. In T. Skillington, & A. Setti (Eds.), *Climate Change Resilience Across Societal Contexts: Challenges, Potentials and Visions for the Future* (1 ed., pp. 155-174). (Energy, Climate and the Environment). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-95020-9_9
- The data is stored in the group files (P) at the University of Helsinki’s server, not yet fully anonymized and in the future, the plan is to open it.